

Paolo Orsi, «un modestissimo cultore della epigrafia»: Paolo Orsi's contribution to Sicilian epigraphy as illustrated by the newly published *taccuini**

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«Io non sono che un modestissimo cultore della epigrafia greca...». With these words, Paolo Orsi sought a particularly esoteric epigraphic favour from Gaetano de Sanctis – the formal transliteration into the Greek alphabet of his transcription of a pair of Sikel texts from Adrano, so that the Palermo linguist Oreste Nazari might then attempt an interpretation¹. Nazari himself had declined to work from Orsi's transcription, protesting that he himself was no epigrapher, but a linguist. Orsi was, of course, engaged in a rhetorical act to elicit de Sanctis' assistance (and the context is important, coming only months after a deeply embarrassing episode in which Orsi invited de Sanctis to study a newly discovered example of the Taormina account inscriptions and Antonio Salinas had intervened by telegram to prevent de Sanctis from doing so when he had already travelled to Taormina from Turin)².

The publication of the first volume of the edited reproductions of Orsi's famous *taccuini* both inspires and enables an attempt to assess Orsi the epigrapher³. The first four *taccuini* alone (out of 150 surviving) include the careful transcription and documentation of at least 412 inscriptions. As Margherita Guarducci observed at Orsi's death in 1935, «la massima parte delle iscrizioni onde si è arricchito il patrimonio epigrafico della Sicilia nell'ultimo cinquantennio siano dovute agli scavi ed alle scoperte di Paolo Orsi»⁴. It is possible to add a little more substance to this comment. When Orsi arrived in Siracusa in September 1888, Mommsen had just published *CIL X.2* (1883), and Kaibel's *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae = Inscriptiones Graecae XIV* (1890) was in final preparation; between them they published 1,177 texts (*addenda* included; *instrumenta* excluded), capturing most of the known material at that date. By my count, Orsi himself published a staggering 812 inscriptions from the island between 1889 and 1933, virtually all of which were previously

* I am immensely grateful to Prof.ssa Pelagatti for the invitation and encouragement to attempt this paper. A very much simpler set of first thoughts was presented at Siracusa, 10 September 2018 on the occasion of the publication of the volume here considered. That event was presided over by the late Sebastiano Tusa (the last occasion on which I saw him), and it seems fitting to dedicate this study of Orsi to the memory of one who, like Orsi, did so much for the archaeology of Sicily. It has been challenging preparing this piece in the unusual circumstances of 2020, and I must express my gratitude to friends and colleagues, at the Bodleian Library and in Sicily, who have provided me with copies of many of the things cited here, against the odds. My final thanks go to dott.ssa Angela Maria Manenti, whose hard work and kindness lies behind every single discovery I have made in the museum at Siracusa, a veritable *sine qua non*. Much of the research for this paper was conducted within the framework of the Crossreads project, which has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 885040).

¹ The letter of 2 June 1912 to de Sanctis is quoted in Accame, 1970, p. 692; cf. *NSA*, 1912, p. 417.

² Accame, 1970 documents the episode in full.

³ Orsi, Lamagna, Monterosso, 2018.

⁴ Guarducci, 1935, p. 299; she declined to attempt any sort of estimate.

unpublished⁵. As we shall see below, he fully documented [p.123] hundreds more in the *Taccuini*, which were either already published or remain unpublished. Nonetheless, his role as even a «modestissimo cultore della epigrafia» has been scarcely considered and certainly deserves greater recognition.

1. Paolo Orsi l'epigrafista?

Explicit discussions of Orsi as an epigrapher are rare. The only one to address his specific contribution to Sicilian epigraphy was Margherita Guarducci, in a very few pages in the volume compiled at his death in 1935, and she began: «Paolo Orsi non fu un epigrafista vero e proprio. Nè egli pretese mai di essere considerato tale; chè anzi, con quello spirito di onestà e di esatta valutazione dell'opera propria che possedette in altissimo grado, sempre riconobbe di non essere addentro ai segreti dell'arte epigrafica... »⁶. Notwithstanding the fact that, as noted already, she was explicit about the scale of his contribution, the overall tone is maintained throughout, emphasising his practice of consulting 'true' epigraphers (such as Halbherr, Comparetti or de Sanctis – or herself) and attributing to him the belief that «le iscrizioni illuminano di diretta e spesso vivissima luce i risultati degli scavi... ». Guarducci was herself a student of Halbherr, Orsi's friend, contemporary and compatriot from Rovereto, and she emerged at the forefront of a new 'school' of Greek epigraphy and it is, in the end, difficult not to attribute some elements of this assessment, and the lack of recognition granted to Orsi *qua* epigraphist, to the evolution of the disciplines of archaeology and epigraphy, and the status of formal academic positions in Italy. Put simply, epigraphy came to be seen from precisely the 1880s as an academic discipline of the universities, and Orsi at precisely the same moment held to the path of the militant archaeologist, in the *soprintendenza*, rather than a university, while his peers such as Halbherr took university positions⁷.

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A rather clearer sense of this can be derived from the invaluable discussion of ancient history and epigraphy, 'il caso italiano' by Giovanni Salmeri⁸. Orsi is conspicuous by his near total absence, and it is worth examining the reasons. On the one hand, Salmeri was explicitly considering Italian archaeological activity beyond Italy, and therefore Orsi's Sicilian activity formally falls outside the discussion. On the other, the concentration is very much upon the holders of university posts, and the development of 'schools', which in turn depends upon tracing academic lineages. Orsi's deeply unsatisfactory relationship with the Faculty at Catania, his ultimate resolution not to accept posts elsewhere, and the lack of any academic

⁵ This count includes texts on stone and metal (including painted catacomb inscriptions), but not inscribed or painted texts on pottery or other *instrumenta domestica*. It was compiled from Orsi's complete bibliography (Marchese, Marchese, 2000), and I have been able to page through every relevant publication there listed (approximately 80 of which contain Sicilian inscriptions), either physically or digitally (excluding minor publications such as reviews or pieces in magazines and more popular works). It is doubtless not a perfect count, but I would suggest that it is probably accurate +/- 10. The count will, eventually, be reproducible via bibliographic search on *I.Sicily* (<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>), but there is much work still to be done to complete that. Note that Orsi additionally published a not insignificant number of texts from Calabria, which I do not include here.

⁶ Guarducci, 1935, p. 297. This judgement seems to me excessive: Orsi never claimed to be a historian (e.g. Orsi, 1904, p. 174 «Essendo archeologico e non storico il mio compito... »); but he certainly never rejected the label of epigrapher, seeing epigraphy as a central part of his archaeological activity.

⁷ On Orsi and Halbherr, see Maurina, Sorge, 2010; Vistoli, 2018, p. 306 highlights the specific case of the chair of archaeology at Rome for which Orsi applied unsuccessfully in 1889, a moment which is further contextualised in La Rosa, 1978 (see below).

⁸ Salmeri, 1986.

successors mean that he is effectively marginalised in such a discussion⁹. Orsi is only introduced at the very end, with reference to «un tipo di formazione che potrebbe definirsi archeologico-antiquaria», which culminated in «l'iniziazione all'archeologia militante da parte del soprintendente di Siracusa Paolo Orsi», and which is suggested as the context for the work of Biagio Pace. The evasive summation of Orsi that follows only reinforces the image: «Data la ricchezza e la novità del lavoro scientifico di Orsi, non è qui possibile tracciarne neppure un quadro sommario. Va solo ricordato che lo studioso, pur avendo indagato soprattutto le fasi preistoriche e protostoriche dell'antichità siciliana, non trascurò i periodi greco e romano e dedicò un particolare attenzione a quello bizantino»¹⁰. The absence of any mention at all of Orsi's epigraphic activity is additionally striking, given the focus of the paper¹¹. And yet, I would suggest, Orsi deserves to be considered quite directly alongside the school of 'archeologi-epigrafisti' (including Guarducci) which Salmeri documents as deriving from Comparetti and Halbherr, and is in turn contrasted with de Sanctis' largely unarchaeological approach – and with all three of whom Orsi in turn corresponded on matters epigraphical.

However, we should first step back a moment to consider Orsi's own formation, both for its epigraphical elements and for the points of divergence from some of his contemporaries. Unlike his contemporary Halbherr, who studied at Rome, and went on to Florence with Comparetti, Orsi studied at Padua and Vienna¹². La Rosa, with his emphasis upon Orsi's role in the evolution of archaeology at Catania, and 'archeologia militante', observes that [p.125] his formal enrolment at Vienna for the second year of his laurea, in 1878-79, offered «un contenuto più archeologico e tecnico alla sua formazione» than Padua could provide (where he took his laurea in 1882), and where 'militant archaeology' was lacking¹³. However, as Zanotti-Bianco observed more precisely in his lyrical eulogy of Orsi, «si fosse specializzato a Vienna con l'Hirschfeld in epigrafia romana»¹⁴. It is tempting to note the parallel here with Degrassi, whom Salmeri notes was a pupil (1907-1911) of the 'Mommsenian' E. Bormann at Vienna, and whose career, the true beginning of Latin epigraphy in Italy, began «da una formazione di epigrafista più specifica di quella che a Roma potevano offrire Gatti, Vaglieri e De Ruggerio... », who held the first formal epigraphic roles at Rome from the late 1880s (along with Halbherr in Greek)¹⁵.

Gianfranco Paci has provided a more detailed examination of Orsi's earliest epigraphic activity, in the context of his university studies¹⁶. The nineteen-year-old Orsi's first publication was a contribution to Otto Hirschfeld's 'Epigraphische Mittheilungen', in Hirschfeld and Benndorf's *Archaeologisch-epigraphische Mittheilungen aus Oesterreich* for

⁹ On Orsi's position at Catania, see La Rosa, 1978.

¹⁰ Salmeri, 1986, pp. 227-228.

¹¹ A picture that is curiously further reinforced in the contribution of Arias, 1976, which sets out to consider four areas of Orsi's work, of which the fourth is to be «i documenti cristiani e bizantini» (p. 16); and yet this fourth is somehow simply forgotten, and the piece concludes by summing up the *three* themes discussed.

¹² Carinci, 2000 for Halbherr's university studies, and cf. Sorge, 2010.

¹³ La Rosa, 1978, pp. 489-497 documents Orsi's archaeological formation, with pp. 494-495 specifically on the curriculum of his laurea; the emphasis on archaeology again leads to the unfortunate minimising of any reference to epigraphic study in this discussion.

¹⁴ Zanotti-Bianco, 1935, p. 16.

¹⁵ Salmeri, 1986, p. 214.

¹⁶ Paci, 1991, but see also Maurina, 2010, esp. p. 20.

1878, and here already the 'militant epigraphist' is on clear display¹⁷. The piece, published under Hirschfeld's name, is introduced thus: «Herr Paolo Orsi aus Rovereto, Mitglied des epigraphischen Seminars, hat in diesem Sommer folgende in Südtirol in den letzten Jahren gefundenen Inschriften copirt... ». Orsi's contribution is clearly distinguished and is already a precise catalogue of epigraphic texts and their contexts of the sort that will become very familiar; and is not lacking in interpretation and analysis. At the end of his first year, in the summer of 1878, Orsi was already proposing to publish a corpus of the inscriptions of the Trentino (and the unpublished manuscript from 1879 survives)¹⁸. Over the following years this approach, combining epigraphy, topography, numismatics and more can be seen to evolve, the distinctively Orsian approach to 'militant archaeology' developing, reflected in a steady stream of publication¹⁹. As Paci comments «Così che, se si volesse inquadrare [p.126] la figura dello studioso che emerge da questi lavori, non all'epigrafista di dovrà pensare e neppure, forse, all'archeologo, quanto piuttosto al topografo. Si tratta però di un studioso di topografia antica straordinariamente attento – e in ciò si vede l'influsso della scuola viennese – ai documenti epigrafici».²⁰ The phrase 'scoperte archeologico-epigrafiche' appears more than once in the titles of these early publications, offering a sense of the author's focus, and in December 1882, a few months after completing his laurea, Orsi was seeking Luigi Pigorini's support with the Ministero della Pubblica Istruzione, to undertake study at Rome «... per avere qualche lieve sussidio onde poter continuare per qualche mese in Roma gli studi archeologici-epigrafici ai quali mi sono avviato».²¹

Paci concludes his study by noting that, with Orsi's move to first Rome in 1884, then the library at Florence in 1885, this research was effectively abandoned. This is, however, not entirely true, and there is a stronger thread of epigraphic continuity to be traced: in part this lies in the continued friendship and collaboration with Halbherr – and the developing association with Comparetti during his time in Florence²²; but in part it is also quite simply a continuity of the interests and studies fostered already in Vienna. Halbherr on the other hand studied in Rome, not Vienna, and then took up the challenge set out by Comparetti to develop an Italian school of Greek epigraphy through his work in Crete (to which Orsi participated in these early years)²³. In 1888 Comparetti wrote of the need firstly for Italian study in and of ancient Greece, but secondly of the need for an Italian school of Greek epigraphy – which he saw initiated in the figure of his student Halbherr²⁴. In recounting this, Salmeri observes «Il sentimento do orgoglio nazionale che stette alla base della scelta epigrafica di Comparetti fu condiviso in quegli anni anche da altri nostri studiosi di discipline storiche e filologiche»²⁵. [p.127]

¹⁷ Orsi, 1878; Paci, 1991, p. 211 refers to «una militanza epigrafica» and it seems not inappropriate.

¹⁸ Paci, 1991, p. 207 quotes from Orsi's diary of June 1878, p. 69; cf. Maurina, 2010, p. 21.

¹⁹ E.g. Orsi 1881; 1882; 1883 (see Marchese, Marchese, 2000 for the complete bibliography of Orsi).

²⁰ Paci, 1991, p. 210.

²¹ The letter of December 1882 to Pigorini is quoted in Cupitò, Facchin, Leonardi, 2010, p. 55 n. 106.

²² La Rosa, 1978, p. 496; La Rosa speculates on the influence of Comparetti upon Orsi between 1885 and 1888, noting (n. 143) the potential of the archive of Comparetti's correspondence at Florence for further research in this area. He adduces the later instances of correspondence and consultation between the two, particularly on matters epigraphic: see e.g. *MAL* 1, 1890, cols. 787-788; *NSA*, 1912, pp. 451-454; *NSA*, 1920, p. 336.

²³ See e.g. Sorge, 2010 with further references.

²⁴ Comparetti, 1888, p. 648: «Parvemi che questi studi epigrafici, ormai per la ragione che ho detta divenuti essenzialissimi, per la parte greca almeno, in Italia fossero troppo negletti e mi diedi a coltivarli nella speranza di trovar qualche allievo che bene avviato a quelli e fatto poi specialista, superasse il maestro... ».

²⁵ Cf. Salmeri, 1986, p. 216.

This sentiment was in fact explicitly shared by Orsi himself. Just as he was moving to Siracusa, in 1888, Orsi penned a striking pair of reviews, on Bormann's *CIL XI* and Pais' *Supplementum* to *CIL*²⁶. In the latter he deplores the state of Italian epigraphic studies in recent decades (tracing an Italian tradition back to Cyriac of Ancona!), while praising the new series instituted by Pais and the chairs newly established at Rome; in the former, after praising the Berlin corpus, he concludes «non è esaurito il campo delle discipline epigrafiche, e noi Italiani potremmo modestamente tentare un'impresa nazionale, di più limitate proporzioni, se si vuole, ma pur sempre desideratissima e di incalcolabile utilità... ». Noteworthy is his further observation, in light of De Rossi's *ICUR* project, that «... la grande congerie delle altre iscrizioni cristiane, sparse dovunque in Italia deve o prima o poi richiamare l'attenzione dei dotti, e determinare la pubblicazione di un *Corpus* speciale ancora per esse, arrivando al secolo jx, o meglio a tutto il x... ». Furthermore, at a distance of fifteen years, he was able to claim that he, together with Joseph Führer, had made a start on this²⁷.

The lengthy review of *CIL XI*, in particular, deserves a place in any assessment of Orsi 'the epigrapher'. It is a review that could be written today, and demonstrates a remarkable sense of the scope and potential not only of epigraphy, but of its systematic study:

«L'utile derivante da questa inesausta miniera di documenti si fa già da alcuni anni sentire dalla rivoluzione portata nel modo di concepire e di scrivere la storia imperiale soprattutto, e quella delle istituzioni coloniali e municipali. Ma se questi sono i risultati precipui e d'ordine generale cui si arriva con lo studio del nuovo apparato epigrafico, altri ve ne hanno particolari ma non meno apprezzabili, che di volo qui ricorderemo, e che spettano alla topografia, toponomastica, onomatologia e se vuoi anche alla statistica ed all'etnografia.»²⁸

In the following pages, he makes good on these claims, considering in detail the statistical distributions which can be documented through the volume, [p.128] endeavouring to set them against Beloch's demographic estimates, speculating on the implications of low epigraphic density, rates of urbanisation, and the implications of all of this for the penetration of Roman culture – it is a discussion from epigraphic evidence that would shame many more recent papers on 'romanisation'. This is followed by considerations of onomastic evidence, the niceties of Ravenna's institutional history (in dialogue with Mommsen) and much else besides.

However, more than this, it is possible to see glimpses of Orsi endeavouring to put this into practice within the University context, as his peers were doing elsewhere. Orsi was formally accredited to the Faculty at Catania on 12 December 1889 as «privata docenza con effetti legali in Archeologia» (the original request and proposal having been made and approved in June/July 1889). As La Rosa has elucidated, his appointment belongs precisely within the

²⁶ Orsi, 1887-1888; 1888. The former was published in the second fascicle (July-December) for 1888, and Orsi is listed in the volume as 'socio corrispondente' of the Deputazione di Storia Patria per le Province di Romagna, and as based in Siracusa. Consulting Orsi's bibliography (Marchese, Marchese 2000), it is apparent that Orsi continued to review epigraphic works throughout his career, e.g. *ICUR I*, in *ASSic*, 46, 1925, pp. 182-184.

²⁷ The observation is recalled in Orsi, 1904, p. 189, noting a similar appeal of De Rossi in 1877 for someone to study the Syracusan material; and he could assert that he and Joseph Führer answered the call.

²⁸ Orsi, 1887-1888, p. 242; this is decidedly more ambitious than the view imputed to him by Guarducci, quoted above.

context of the contemporary creation of teaching positions in archaeology in other Italian universities (beginning with Salinas at Palermo, 1865/66), often directly bound up also with epigraphy, not least at precisely this date at Rome²⁹. In his second year of teaching at Catania (1890-1891), the examinations in archaeology covered in one case: «Sistemi di calchi; esplorazioni epigrafiche. Varie forme adottate nelle epigrafi ad indicare i numeri»; and in another «enumerazioni di alcuni titoli arcaici. Le epigrafi funebri e loro caratteri»³⁰.

Furthermore, it is in this period and in the specific field of Christian epigraphy that we find Orsi's only pupil who made some inroads on an academic career - and one to whom he laid claim, both in his unsuccessful request for promotion to 'straordinario' at Catania in 1896, and in his address to the historical congress of 1903³¹. Vincenzo Strazzulla enrolled at Catania in 1889, the same year that Orsi began teaching, and completed his laurea in 1893, before publishing work on the Christian epigraphy of Siracusa, dedicated to his 'insigni Magistro', Orsi³².

The case should, however, not be overstated; Orsi rapidly abandoned his pursuit of the path of university academia, in favour of the path of [p.129] militant archaeology which his position at Siracusa enabled³³. However, what I have attempted to illustrate thus far is that epigraphy held a central place in both his training and his academic interests and ambitions, and that it held a very live place in his thoughts precisely as he took up his new position - with some initial ambivalence - in Siracusa, arriving on 7 September 1888³⁴. What I will attempt to demonstrate in the third part of this paper, after first considering the new publication which has made this possible, is the extent to which the newly published edition of the first four volumes of Orsi's *taccuini* reveals with much greater clarity Orsi's 'militanza epigrafica' (of considerable calibre), no less than his 'archeologia militante'.

2. Orsi's *taccuini* in published form

With the publication by Gioconda Lamagna and Giuseppina Monterosso of a photographic reproduction and transcription of the first four notebooks of Paolo Orsi, it is to be hoped that we enter upon a new phase of appreciation of Orsi's remarkable activity. The significance of the notebooks has hardly been underestimated in the past: the editorial preface to this new volume, itself produced under the auspices of the Accademia dei Lincei, rightly quotes a vote of the Consiglio Superiore delle Antichità e Belle Arti of 16 November 1962, on the occasion of the formal acquisition of the notebooks by the state, which concludes «che tali Taccuini vengano destinati al Museo Nazionale di Siracusa, dove costituiranno la più preziosa

²⁹ La Rosa, 1978, p. 469-472 and esp. n. 24 for the teaching of epigraphy at Rome.

³⁰ La Rosa, 1978, p. 535 no. 37, «Estratto dei Verbali di esame in Archeologia...».

³¹ Letter of 12 March 1896 (La Rosa, 1978, p. 520 no. 8); and Orsi, 1904, p. 190, «un giovane siciliano, il prof. V. Strazzulla, mio discepolo».

³² Strazzulla, 1897, frontispiece, «Paulo Orsi, insigni magistro ob animi grates D»; and at p. 63 in the *prolegomena*, discussing previous work, he comments: «Paucas quidem immutationes adieci epitaphiis a Paulo Orsi pervulgatis, in ipsis enim raras quandoquidem discrepantias a marmoreis vel calcariensibus lapidibus, ut aestimo, inveni. Pariterque Graecas inscriptiones a Georgio Kaibelio et Latinas a Theodoro Mommseno...». La Rosa, 1978, p. 506-507 for further references, noting the limitations to Strazzulla's work (of which Orsi was also aware); Strazzulla died early, in 1909.

³³ La Rosa, 1978, p. 479-489 traces his relationship to the Faculty at Catania and his academic positions in detail; cf. Vistoli, 2018, p. 306.

³⁴ See Vistoli, 2018, p. 300-303 for Orsi's transition to Siracusa.

testimonianza dell'attività ineguagliabile del grande esploratore e studioso e uno strumento ancora utile di consultazioni per ulteriori ricerche»³⁵. The value of Orsi's notebooks, not simply as a memorial of his work, but as a unique research tool of considerable importance, has been stressed – and illustrated - by multiple scholars in the years since, whether in the work by S.L. Agnello on the catacomb of Vigna Cassia, or P. Pelagatti for multiple sites across the south-east of Sicily, or A.M. Marchese returning in detail to the catacomb of Vigna Cassia³⁶. However, the notebooks have, until now, remained largely unstudied beyond the circle [p.130] of their immediate keepers, and of only limited accessibility in the Museo Archeologico Regionale P. Orsi, in Siracusa.

At the same time, the publication of the notebooks is itself a major challenge and undertaking. The surviving notebooks number 150, each containing between 70 and 130 pages of Orsi's (or sometimes his collaborators') dense, neat writing and drawings – a total in excess of 10,000 pages³⁷. For all that the handwriting, commonly first in pencil and then inked in subsequently, is lucid, it is not always easy to read; and as past publications have emphasised, much of the value lies in the drawings, not the text, meaning that mere transcription is far from adequate. Successive directors (Giuseppe Voza, Concetta Ciurcina, Beatrice Basile, Gioconda Lamagna) of the Siracusa museum have overseen the copying of the notebooks first to microfilm and then to digital format; but also the far more laborious task (and one requiring significant knowledge and expertise) of transcription and indexing. That work was formally completed in 2013, paving the way for the series of which this volume is but the first.

A work of this sort entails hard choices, and it is impossible to please everyone³⁸. Two aspects in particular are likely to split readers – the first, the decision to separate the transcription of the text from the reproduction of the pages; and the second, the renunciation of a supporting commentary, or even bibliographic annotation. Both decisions are justified and explained by the editors: the former in order better to facilitate the page-by-page reproduction of the notebooks at readable size; the latter, because the preparation of meaningful commentary or annotation would have delayed the project beyond reason³⁹. The separation of the transcription from the reproduction requires the reader to move frequently back and forth, but equally, the ability to page through the originals with two double-pages to a single page in the reproduction, with all the pagination clearly labelled is no less useful. The reproductions themselves are in a clean and legible grayscale, avoiding expensive colour reproduction, which would have added limited value (occasional uses of red ink or annotations in blue or red pencil are obscured but otherwise the volumes are essentially black and white)⁴⁰. Although not precisely to scale, the reproductions are in fact close to life-size (the original pages being in general 15-16 cm high by 10 cm wide; the reproductions are consistently resized to 14.2 x 8.6 cm). As one who has used this first volume extensively, in

³⁵ Orsi, Lamagna and Monterosso 2018, v (from *BdA*, 1962, fasc. 4, p. 378).

³⁶ For example, Agnello, 1961; Pelagatti, 1966; Orsi, Pelagatti, 1967-1968; Marchese, 2012; a full summary of previous publications directly exploiting and/or reproducing parts of the notebooks is provided by Monterosso in Orsi, Lamagna, Monterosso, 2018, pp. xxv-xxviii.

³⁷ See further Lamagna, in Orsi, Lamagna, Monterosso, 2018, pp. x-xiii.

³⁸ For a typical, largely positive, review, see Parra, 2019.

³⁹ Orsi, Lamagna, Monterosso, 2018, pp. vii and xxix.

⁴⁰ Lamagna, in Orsi, Lamagna, Monterosso, 2018, p. xi.

the attempt to identify the inscriptions noted here by Orsi, it is difficult to dispute the decision to avoid annotation and commentary – having attempted [p.131] just one small part of it, the task is onerous in the extreme, and the variety of knowledge and skills required, given the variety of material, would have made the undertaking immense and the delay would have been lengthy if not permanent. At the same time, the volume has made the task incomparably easier for one with a specific aim like my own, combining as it does clear pagination and basic indexing, clear reproduction of the original, and a sound transcription⁴¹.

It is difficult to fault the quality of the publication and the immense effort already undertaken, and one can readily accept the choices made by the editors. The more fundamental question perhaps remains as to whether the unwieldy format of 24 x 34 cm in a soft cover, combined with the price, makes this the ideal solution for the dissemination and exploitation of Orsi's lifetime work (at 125 Euros, taking the first volume as standard, the complete set, presumably running to at least 37 volumes, implies a total cost of almost 5,000 euros, almost a metre's shelving and a weight of more than 40 kg). Given the existence already of high quality digital scans, and the desirability, over time, of providing supporting information or annotation (rather than requiring any scholar who approaches the volumes to repeat the work of identification and bibliographic investigation which others may already have undertaken), a digital solution, perhaps using the increasingly widely adopted International Image Interoperability Framework, which would facilitate viewing, comparison and annotation of the pages, might ultimately be of greater value⁴². The one format does not, of course, preclude the other⁴³.

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3. Orsi the epigraphist, in light of *Taccuini* 1-4.

The first four volumes of the notebooks cover the period from April 1888, when Orsi was still employed as sub-librarian, second class, at the Biblioteca Nazionale in Florence, through to the conclusion of excavations at Megara Hyblaea on 11 May 1889 and work at Cassibile and Siracusa in June of that year⁴⁴. The first 37 pages of volume 1 contain a variety of annotations and extracts from materials in the Florence library; with page 38 we arrive, with Orsi, in Siracusa: top left of the page, alongside the heading «Museo Archeologico di Siracusa» is the date, 9 September 1888 (Orsi arrived on the 7th). Several readers have

⁴¹ The transcription frequently clarifies text which to me is illegible; I have however noted occasional slips in the reading of numerals when checking inventory numbers, which doubtless reflects the decision not to annotate the transcription or control systematically the original against other publications. I include those which I noted: Tacc. 1, p. 89, read 35 for 95; 1, p. 93 read 207 for 107; 1, p. 94 read 168 for 165; 1, p. 106 read 265 for 26; 1, p. 134 read 149 for 349, and 5991 for 5994; 1, p. 138 read 78 for 18; 2, p. 18 read 152 for 159.

⁴² <https://iiif.io/about/> (accessed 24.11.2020).

⁴³ Similarly, this article is not intended to be comprehensive in its analysis of the epigraphic material of *Taccuini* 1-4; the complete set of identifications and correspondences compiled in the course of writing this article will instead be incorporated into the data in *I.Sicily* (<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>), as part of the longer term project of cataloguing the epigraphic collection of the Museo Archeologico Regionale P.Orsi, and the epigraphic corpus for Sicily as a whole. It will, in due course, be possible to access a complete concordance of the inscriptions recorded in this volume through the bibliographic search tool in the *I.Sicily* corpus.

⁴⁴ The last dated activity in *Taccuino* 4 is 19 June 1889 (p. 79); the inscription recorded on p. 95 was entered in the inventory (inv. 7261) on 28 July. *Taccuino* 4's organisation is complicated by the fact that the final part of the Megara excavations are recorded from the back of the notebook forwards (pp. 133-106). A chronological table of the years covered by the notebooks is provided at Orsi, Lamagna, Monterosso, 2018, p. xii; and a general summary of contents is tabulated at p. xx.

remarked that Orsi's record of his Syracusan residency begins by formally noting the Museum personnel (himself included), their roles, and their salaries as of 15 September 1888, which he does on p. 39. However, this is not where the Sicilian story begins: the very first and immediate entry, on p. 38, is a drawing of an inscription, described as a damaged block of marble with traces of an inscription, and with the annotation «all'agorà» (i.e. the former Piazza d'Armi, the modern 'Villini' on Corso Umberto I). The inscription features in the first of Orsi's many contributions to the *Notizie degli Scavi di Antichità*, «Scoperte archeologico-epigrafiche nella città e provincia di Siracusa», published in the November fascicle of the volume for 1889 (signed off on 15 December 1889 by Fiorelli)⁴⁵. In other words, within 48 hours of arriving in Siracusa Orsi was already recording inscriptions that he found in the city. No less worthy of note is the fact that the first of his contributions to the *Notizie* continues, in both its title and its form, in the tradition of his earlier publications in the *Archäologisch-Epigraphische Mitteilungen*, and the *Archivio Trentino* cited above. Comparison of the entry in the *NSA* furthermore provides an immediate and clear example of what the *Taccuini* provide, which the more constrained *Notizie* format generally does not, at least for the epigraphic material, namely a drawing [Fig. 1: Tacc. 1, p. 38]⁴⁶. Most unusually for Orsi, there is no fuller description [p.133] of the stone, and no dimensions were recorded. It is impossible not to imagine the 30-year old Orsi instantly out and about in the new city, exploring and recording impulsively before anything else is done.

More was to follow, however, under the (Latin) heading «Siraculis in Museo» (*Taccuino* 1, p. 40), in a burst of epigraphic activity which is scarcely captured by the only note of it in print, Zanotti Bianco's list of Orsi's activity in Siracusa, which begins «Ne raccoglie appena arrivato [in Siracusa] le epigrafi superstiti...»⁴⁷. With the exception of pp. 72-77 (a brief note on clandestine excavations at Megara Hyblaea), the entire remainder of *Taccuino* 1 (to p. 138) is devoted to epigraphic material, as are the first 74 pages of *Taccuino* 2 [p.134] (inscriptions, amphora stamps, and miscellaneous marks). The initial guiding principle is not immediately clear: pp. 40-50 gather together a miscellany of material, most – but not all – already included in the inventory either of Sogliano (nos. 1-5990) or Cavallari (nos. 5991-8434), and acquired in the preceding years of the 1880s (the earliest date noted is 1884, the latest 1888, but not all are dated)⁴⁸. This is followed, on pp. 51-72, by an extensive series of material under the heading «Fondo dei rifiuti e scarti epigrafici del Museo Archeologico di Siracusa». The first of these is noted as from Epipolae, in large regular Greek letters (ISic003402, no inv.), but the rest are placed into a numbered sequence, with dimensions and a drawing of the text, from 1-90. All consist of a handful of letters over 1 or more lines, and although some of them have now been identified in the museum stores, as far as I can tell

⁴⁵ Orsi, 1889; Zanotti Bianco, 1935, p. 22 offers an evocative portrayal of Orsi's rigorous compilation of his «manipoli» for the *Notizie*, based upon the *Taccuini*.

⁴⁶ Orsi, 1889, p. 371. The inscription, as is apparent from the annotation «all'agora» in the notebook, and the statement «presso il pozzo dell'Ingegnere... fu segnalato...» in the *Notizie*, was not recovered and appears now to be lost. It has never, to my knowledge, been noted subsequently (see now ISic001667; all references to ISic numbers can be resolved in the form: <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic000000>).

⁴⁷ Zanotti Bianco, 1935, p. 17.

⁴⁸ Some are Latin pieces recorded in the 200s in the inventory (Sogliano), together with inv. 920; some are Greek texts registered in the 6000s (Cavallari), although two belong to the very beginning, inv. 6 and 7; three are from Akrai, of which two were only registered in the 12000s (Orsi); and one is a catacomb piece (inv. 11170); only the final piece of this group (ISic000727, in *Tacc.* 1, p. 50) remains unidentified in the inventory, although it has now been located in the museum stores.

none of them were included in the inventory⁴⁹. The vast majority are Greek and appear comparable to the catacomb material. After number 68 Orsi, perhaps understandably, revised his ambition: «Di molti altri frammentini cemenziali contenenti 3, 4, 5 lettere non vennero fatti gli apografi, perché ritenuti inutili, soprattutto dopo che, studiate le forme paleografiche e le specie del marmo dei medesimi, venne eliminata ogni possibilità di ricostruzione»⁵⁰. A handful of slightly more substantial funerary fragments follow (nos. 69-75), before a final section (nos. 76-90) described as «frammenti di grandi (perlopiù monumentali) iscrizioni di epoca imperiale romana, che dalla grafia si giudicano dei secoli I-III»; all are Latin. In most cases, Orsi records the height of the letters also (ranging from 6.5-13.5 cm). A brief aside on «scavi clandestini» undertaken in «this month of September» in Megara Hyblaea follows – and which, in turn, implies that the 111 texts recorded up to this point were all documented within the first three weeks of Orsi's arrival in Siracusa. The rest of *Taccuino* 1 (pp. 78-138) is then taken up by a continuous series of epigraphic transcriptions, under the heading «Sala Cristiana»; almost every text is detailed with its inventory number (and where the number is missing, I have been able to identify it, primarily because of the clarity of Orsi's own record), and this sequence continues uninterrupted to p. 27 of *Taccuino* 2. In these pages Orsi provides an accurate transcription (in the form of a lucid and accurate drawing [p.135] of the text), with basic measurements, of every single inscription in the museum's inventory from 11 to 223, with only three omissions⁵¹. The coverage of the Latin material listed under inv. 229 to 294 is slightly less complete (some 35 texts are transcribed) but still extensive. In other words, what the *Taccuini* now reveal is a truly remarkable undertaking, in which, during his first two months at Siracusa, Orsi documented some 390 texts⁵².

If Orsi were no epigraphist, and this were little more than a listing, this would perhaps be less worthy of remark, effectively a repetition and supplement of the existing inventory. But these are accurate, careful transcriptions, utterly superior to the existing inventory (and the publications in the contemporary corpora, as will be seen below); and a plan, with a clear vision of what is and is not published, can in fact be discerned⁵³. Summing up his activity over the first three *lustra* of his time at Siracusa, at the Historical Congress of 1903, Orsi surveyed the results of his work across eastern Sicily. While incidentally noting epigraphic finds he had made at other locations, he concludes the overview of work at Siracusa with specific observations on the epigraphy: «mi fermo ai titoli classici, onde negli ultimi anni si accrebbe l'epigrafia siracusana; si era sperato di trarne gran messe dalla demolizioni delle grandiose fortificazioni dei tempi di Carlo V e di Filippo II, costruite in parte con materiale antico; ma tali speranze vennero frustrate. Non vanno oltre la quarantina i titoli classici da me pubblicati in *Notizie*, 1889, p. 369 [etc.] ... invece fu abbondantissima la messe dei titoli

⁴⁹ With the exception of numbers 69 and 70, which were added retrospectively in the later 1940s as inv. 47581 and 47582.

⁵⁰ The challenge is even greater now, the quantity of epigraphic fragments of this sort held in the stores having increased considerably.

⁵¹ Inventory numbers 17, 20 and 42 are omitted; number 42 is currently located in the catacomb materials in store in the museum; 17 and 20 (IG XIV.33 and 38 respectively) are not currently identified.

⁵² Page 41 of the second notebook records autopsy of a text at the Castello Eurialo (ISic000419), on 8 November 1888, offering a *terminus ante quem* for the preceding activity.

⁵³ The weakness of the earlier inventory records, compared to Orsi's, is exemplified by the case of *Taccuino* 1, p. 41 (ISic001668), drawn carefully by Orsi (and noted by him as inv. 232), published in *NSA*, 1889, p. 385, but ultimately re-inventoried as inv. 50779 after the Second World War because of the opacity of the original entry.

cristiani, di cui dirò altrove»⁵⁴. The initial flurry of activity on pp. 40-50 of *Taccuino* 1 gains focus, as fully fourteen out of the twenty-one texts there recorded appeared immediately in the following year's *Notizie* (a fifteenth in *NSA*, 1891, p. 397), and these were in turn almost all incorporated into either the *addenda* of *IG XIV* (1890) or the supplement to *CIL X in Ephemeris Epigraphica VIII* (1899), nos. 679-694. Furthermore, the vast majority of this material is indeed 'titoli classici' and unpublished⁵⁵. This is Orsi pursuing the agenda of [p.136] the preceding years, extending and supplementing the contemporary work of the Berlin corpora⁵⁶; and transforming his notes directly into publication. At the same time, his personal consolidation of the material in the museum, prior to launching himself into the city and its territory, is entirely of a piece with his well-documented methodological approach⁵⁷.

Epigraphic material is more haphazardly scattered through the remainder of *Taccuini* 2-4, but much of it is similarly swept up into the *Notizie* report of 1889 (or that of 1891). Texts in the galleries of Castello Eurialo are noted at 2, p. 42 (ISic000419); a monumental Greek fragment at 2, p. 74 (ISic003043, *NSA* 1889); second-hand reports of texts in the wider Syracusan territory at 2, p. 94-95 (ISic001073 and two others, unidentified); multiple texts seen at Akrai at 2, pp. 106-119 (unpublished, many later appear in Pugliese Carratelli, 1956); a text from Priolo at 2, pp. 131-132 (ISic003372, *NSA* 1891); a Roman text already in the museum, presumably missed in the initial sweep, at 2, p. 135 (inv. 248, ISic004357, *NSA* 1889); texts found during the excavations at Megara, at 4, p. 19 (ISic000368, ISic001439, treated in *MAL* 1, 1890); a monumental text from the amphitheatre at 4, p. 44 (ISic000620, *NSA* 1889); and a Hellenistic fragment found in the ongoing demolition of the fortifications on Ortygia at 4, p. 95 (ISic003401, *NSA* 1889). This last provides a brief glimpse into Orsi's working methods, since on pp. 93-94 we find a heading «Correzioni da introdurre nelle bozze delle scoperte di Siracusa», followed by notes on the amphora stamps which will be published in *NSA*, 1889, p. 379, and the quotation of an «autorevole giudizio dell'Halbherr» on the palaeography of such stamps, doubtless received by correspondence (but which does not seem to have made it, at least explicitly, into the final version). This is in turn followed by the fragment ISic003401 (seen in late June or early July – its entry into the inventory on 28 July is the *terminus ante quem*), introduced by the line «Da inserire nella mia relazione delle *Notizie*». This is followed by further working notes, such as comparanda for the inscribed funerary capital of Kaliseos of Megara on p. 98 (ISic001408, inv. 1), which is clearly being examined in anticipation of the *MAL* 1, 1890 publication, where it is considered alongside the two new [p.137] Megara inscriptions recorded on p. 19. Nonetheless, there is also material published in the *Notizie* for 1889 which does not appear in these *Taccuini*⁵⁸.

⁵⁴ Orsi, 1904, p. 185.

⁵⁵ The six exceptions, omitted from *NSA*, are two catacomb fragments, three pieces from Akrai (two previously published, and republished in *IG XIV*.218 and 222) and a large architectural fragment with Latin letters, already in *CIL X*.7133.

⁵⁶ *NSA*, 1889, p. 383 includes inv. 286 (ISic000426), recorded on *Tacc.* 1, p. 111, a slab from the catacombs bearing an imperial period text: this is (re)published by Orsi explicitly because Mommsen's minimalist record in *CIL X*.7146, apparently derived from Schubring, was deficient, recording only the second line and with no further details (it is a large marble slab, broken in four, intact only at the lower edge, measuring 81 x 41 cm, reading AVG[----] | (vac. 3) Cerialis · Sex[---] | *vacat*). Manganaro republished it again (1989, p. 181-2, no. 61 with fig.65), without acknowledging that Orsi had already read the remnants of the first line correctly.

⁵⁷ Paci, 1991, p. 209-210; Pelagatti, 1991; Vistoli, 2018, p. 303.

⁵⁸ Whether in *Taccuino* 5 (the remainder of 1889) or not, I have been unable to check, but it would clearly be wrong to assume that everything must first feature in the *taccuini* (cf. below n. 81, for a text from Akrai).

Two elements are considered only briefly here, but warrant future study. In *Tacc.* 2, pp. 28-64 an almost uninterrupted sequence of amphora stamps is presented, each carefully drawn; no context or identification is however provided (although multiple stamps are published and discussed in the report in *NSA*, 1889, and this was the subject of the communication with Halbherr noted on *Tacc.* 4, pp. 93-94). Secondly, a fascinating sequence of material in *Tacc.* 2, pp. 64-74. As Orsi noted, in the statement quoted from his 1904 synthesis above, he held out great hopes for the potential contribution to the epigraphic material which the ongoing demolition of the Spanish fortifications of Ortygia might yield – hopes which were largely disappointed⁵⁹. A number of inscriptions were indeed recovered from these works, including two recorded in these notebooks (*Tacc.* 2, p. 74 = ISic003043, and 4, p. 95 = ISic003401), and five are gathered into the *NSA* 1889 report (pp. 370-371). However, not elsewhere published or discussed, to the best of my knowledge, is the extensive collection of what appear to be masons' marks from the building blocks of the fortifications, documented only here by Orsi. The drawings are supplemented by a number of comments and observations, including reference to Reinach's *Traité d'épigraphie grecque*⁶⁰. Orsi observes the potential value of palaeography for distinguishing ancient from early modern (i.e. Spanish), while also noting that «Per il Cavallari queste marche sono tutte antiche, per me appena il 5%» (*Tacc.* 2, p. 64; cf. p. 71, «Blocchi letterati tratti da una toretta greca (fenicia per il Cavallari)»); those recorded on the first few pages are mostly dismissed as «spagnoli», but from p. 69, noting significant technical differences in form, what are assumed to be «greci» are documented instead (with observations on p. 70 regarding diverse forms of *omega*). The rich variety of ancient masons' marks, their form and function has only recently begun to receive more intense study in general, and documented Sicilian examples are relatively few (e.g. the *sima* blocks on the temple at Himera, the walls of Erice, and those on various architectural elements at Segesta)⁶¹. Although precise location and context are lacking for these examples, the examination and contextualisation of these examples within the [p.138] wider practice, and in a study of the other Sicilian evidence, could yield useful insights to periods of monumentalisation on Ortygia and for other sites across the city.

This particular sequence of the *taccuini* concludes with the record of a single block found walled into the outermost part of the fortifications, and which bears instead a fragment of a monumental Hellenistic inscription⁶². This offers an excellent example of the contrast between the standardised publication in the *Notizie* and the frequently richer quality of the data provided by Orsi's original 'apograph', especially in the circumstances where the original is so far unrecovered. The plain text report of -]ΣKATA[- in the *Notizie*, notwithstanding the inclusion of dimensions is less rich than the drawing of the letters; more than this, however, aware of the interest and nature of monumental texts, Orsi's original notes

⁵⁹ Orsi, 1904, p. 185. On the demolition of the fortifications, Trigilia, 1985, p. 38ff and Trigilia, 1998 (*non vidi*).

⁶⁰ Reinach, 1885, p. 472 on 'Lettres d'assemblage'.

⁶¹ Weber, 2013 is the most detailed study of Greek practice; cf. Weber, 2015 and Kowalewska, Eisenberg, 2019 for more recent specific studies (earlier general discussions in e.g. Martin, 1965, pp. 221-231). For Himera, cf. Manni Piraino 1973, no.16; for Segesta, Ampolo, Erdas, 2019, nos. G20-G23; for Erice and other Punic examples in Sicily, and wider Punic practice, Mezzolani, 2008, pp. 12-14.

⁶² *Taccuini* 2, p. 74 = *NSA*, 1889, p. 371 = inv. 12254 = ISic003043 (currently not located in the museum stores).

include details of the depth of the letters (14 mm) and the cross-section of the chiselling [Fig. 2: Tacc. 2, p. 74].

The merits of Orsi's epigraphic acumen, as demonstrated by the *Taccuini*, have already been highlighted by Anna Maria Marchese in her restudy of the Vigna Cassia material with the support of the relevant *Taccuini*. She noted that «L'acribia filologica connaturata nel grande archeologo roveretano ci permette, anche per il materiale epigrafico, già sostanzialmente edito, di fare ulteriori puntualizzazioni» (whether for text or context), and that «Gli apografi, inoltre, consentono delle precisazioni riguardo a precedenti ipotesi di lettura»⁶³. That appreciation is strongly reinforced by the opportunity here presented to compare Orsi's transcriptions of the existing museum collection with the editions in the *corpora* and elsewhere (cf. n. 53 above). The devil is in the detail, but Orsi's appreciation of the detail and its significance stands the test; moreover, it has been repeatedly undervalued in the past.

Amongst the earliest entries in the inventory are two fragments of decrees of a *koinon* of the *technitai* of Dionysos. Both were in the process of being included in *IG XIV* (no. 12 = inv. 7, and no. 13 = inv. 6) when Orsi presented editions in *NSA* 1889, p. 384, after transcriptions in *Taccuino* 1, p. 40⁶⁴. Generally the texts are clear and editions diverge little except at [p.139] the margins and in their restorations. As was his general practice, Orsi refrains from substantial attempts at restoration, and here, as often with texts of interest, he incorporates the fruits of his discussion with others (in this case, Halbherr)⁶⁵. The detail to note, on this occasion, is the reading of the first word of the final line of inv. 6, presented by Orsi as [E]ὐεργέταν, with an explicit comment on the Doric accusative included in the publication in *NSA*. Kaibel, who published both texts on the basis of personal autopsy («Descripisi et ex lapide et ex ectypo chartaceo») noted Orsi's edition in his *addenda*, but merely commented on Orsi's reading «v. 6 YEPΓETAN (errore, ni fallor)». Manganaro in turn (incorrectly) stated that Kaibel «erroneamente» [p.140] read YEPΓETAN at line 6, and himself reproduced the reading of YEPΓETHN from his own autopsy⁶⁶. Every single published edition except Orsi's reads -]YEPΓETHN; but the stone, on display in the museum, quite certainly carries an alpha (and while it is a very small point, the persistence of a Doric form in a late Hellenistic text is of significance). In the same discussion, Manganaro went on arbitrarily to correct Orsi's reading of a third, related text, of which Orsi had published a hasty drawing in 1900, prior to its disappearance⁶⁷; on the basis of intuition alone (the stone was at the time lost), Manganaro amended IEPEΩΣ in line 1 to IEPEΩN, with the comment «Si tenga presente che l'Orsi epigrafista è sovente inesatto»⁶⁸. The stone was subsequently rediscovered in Palermo museum, and Orsi's reading can be seen to be quite correct. Manganaro very weakly attempted to justify this wholly unwarranted disparagement of Orsi

⁶³ Marchese, 2012, pp. 22-23.

⁶⁴ ISic000832 and ISic000833 respectively. Le Guen, 2001, p. 320 nos.73 and 74 implies undue criticism of Orsi in highlighting that Orsi believed them to be unpublished having missed the earlier edition of Lüders, 1873, p. 184 no.101a-b (who had it *per litteras* from Richard Engelmann): one of Orsi's principal complaints and reservations when he first arrived at Siracusa was the very poor quality of the bibliographic resources (see e.g. Vistoli, 2018, pp. 307-308, and the letter to Pigorini (26 May 1889) quoted on p. 305).

⁶⁵ Cf. Paci, 1991, p. 211, highlighting the young Orsi's care over the reading, and avoidance of speculative expansion.

⁶⁶ Manganaro, 1963, p. 59 n. 52.

⁶⁷ Orsi, 1900, p. 62 no. 41 (Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas, inv. 8826) = ISic001579.

⁶⁸ Manganaro, 1963, p. 59 n. 54.

by reference to a single other example, Orsi's transcription of a difficult rupestral text outside Adrano, which Manganaro had himself been able to correct in two places – and yet Orsi's was the most accurate text of multiple past attempts, and as Manganaro himself acknowledged, Orsi was the first to read and interpret the text and its main verb εὐφραίνω correctly⁶⁹.

More generally, the quality of Orsi's transcriptions of the material in the first section of the museum's inventory can be tested against contemporary editions. The differences are small, as in the previous examples, but where the direct comparison can be made between, for example, Kaibel's edition in *IG XIV*, Orsi's transcription in the *Taccuini*, and the actual stone, Orsi consistently comes out on top. Five brief examples:

1. *Taccuino* 1, p. 78 = inv. 100 = *IG XIV.159* = ISic000980 [Fig. 3]: Kaibel's text is based upon a hasty report by Mommsen («Descripsit festinans, ut ipse ait, Mommsen»), and among various omissions and slips, most notably this edition includes a Latin P at the start of line 2 (PAYAA...) and a Latin 'b' in line 4 (ΔE TON BION...). Neither of these are present on the stone, and Orsi was able to read the entire text almost without error (he misread the very faintly engraved *beta* in the consular name on line 6 [p. 141] as a *lamda* and missed the very faint initial *lamda* at the start of line 7; but in every other respect it is an accurate and superior reading)⁷⁰.
2. *Taccuino* 2, p. 3(bis) = inv. 28 = *IG XIV.62* = ISic000879 [Fig. 4]: Kaibel's report of the text (unclear whether derived from Carini) is essentially accurate, but omits any indication of the text's features: the monogram for πρὸ in line 3, the ligature on ME in line 4, the dots placed either side of the initial *iota* of Ἰεναρίων at the end of line 5, and the concluding *chi-rho*; Orsi captures them all.
3. *Taccuino* 2, p. 8 = inv. 47 = *IG XIV.92* = ISic000909 [Fig. 5]: Kaibel appears merely to report the text of Carini (although he omits Carini's supporting description), making no reference to the *staurogram* with *sigma* and *omega* (σωτήρ) below, or the flanking doves; furthermore the name Δαφροε, for which Kaibel conjectures alternatives, is clearly Δαφροε, as read by Orsi⁷¹.
4. *Taccuino* 2, p. 2 = inv. 68 = *IG XIV.117* = ISic000934 [Fig. 6]: Kaibel's text («Descripsit Mommsen; utor apographo accuratissimo Ioannis Arezzo di Targia») matches the stone and Orsi's fully, except for a single omission – it appears that only Orsi noted the *nu* at the end of line 5, which although squeezed in above the line is clearly visible (ἐτελεύτησευ).
5. *Taccuino* 1, p. 88 = inv. 110 = *IG XIV.172* = ISic000992 [Fig. 7]: Kaibel, following Mommsen («Descripsit Mommsen») misreports the last letter of line five as a single vertical stroke (with «sic»), and merely notes (but does not accept) Carini's

⁶⁹ Manganaro, 1961, pp. 132-133, on ISic001391 (and Prag, 2015 [2020]), a difficult text to read (I have conducted autopsy myself), *in situ* on the natural rock at Fonte delle Favare, contrada Polichello, 3.5 km NW of the centre of Adrano; Orsi, 1900, p. 44 no. 3 (and Orsi, Pelagatti, 1967-1968, p. 151 for the relevant *taccuino*). Orsi, like many, misread one of the difficult ligatures; but see Manganaro 1961, p. 133 n. 38 for his correct reading of the verb.

⁷⁰ Cf. Ferrua, 1982-1983, p. 18, no. 57, who merely notes the correct consular name and observes that Kaibel's edition has it «male». Note Orsi's comment: «Difficillima lectu; litteris pexumis non sculptis sed quasi graphis exaratis».

⁷¹ Carini, 1872, p. 33, no. V; Carini's description is over the page, perhaps the reason for its omission by Kaibel.

alternative reading of a *delta*; Orsi correctly reads the small raised *delta*, confirming Carini's reading (subsequently adopted also by Agnello)⁷².

[p.145]

Notwithstanding Orsi's rigorous approach to rapid publication, as with the Vigna Cassia material examined by Marchese, these *Taccuini* also include a significant quantity of unpublished material⁷³. As in that case, here too, this consists primarily of very fragmentary material, often not detailed in the museum inventory – primarily the majority of the 90 fragments detailed on *Taccuino* 1, pp. 51-72, which no-one else appears to have had the patience and persistence to document. As with the documentation of the existing collection of the museum, what distinguishes Orsi's transcriptions is their faithfulness to the original. Several of the monumental Latin fragments (*Tacc.* 1, pp. 69-72) can in fact be identified with entries in *CIL* by Mommsen, precisely because both Mommsen and Orsi presented the fragments as drawings (e.g. *CIL* X.7160 = *Taccuino* 1, p.70 no.80 = ISic000439 [Fig. 8]) – although Orsi additionally recorded dimensions and letter heights, which Mommsen did not specify («litteris magnis»)⁷⁴. But in most cases, aligning records of [p.145] one or two letters (such as a C or E) with specific editions is a near hopeless task. Nonetheless, such fragments should hardly be ignored (their omission, not only by Orsi but by most epigraphers, is doubtless as much due to the costs of printing as the minimal amount of information that they convey), and Orsi's gathering together of the monumental Latin fragments is noteworthy: the epigraphic heritage of Siracusa, outside of the catacombs, is in many regards disappointing for a city of its stature in antiquity; however, the multiplicity of fragments of monumental marble texts in Latin, frequently from the area of the Roman forum, attests to an original picture that was rather different and so far unrecognised (and the lack of local marble is doubtless one contributing factor to its loss).

Unpublished material is, however, not entirely limited to fragments. First among the material recorded from the existing collection, on p. 78 of *Taccuino* 1, is inv. 223 (ISic004389) [Fig. 9, cf. Fig. 3], here presented on the basis of autopsy (26.06.2016). This piece is described in the inventory as from «presso Megara Iblea», and in the *Taccuini* as «da Cantera (Melilli)» (presumably [p.147] the area of the Faro Cantera, location of the site antiquarium, where excavations have indicated occupation from antiquity through the Byzantine period, including an early mediaeval chapel)⁷⁵. The piece is a block of the coarse local yellow stone («tufo calcare» in the inventory; «rozzo tufo» in the *Taccuino*), of maximum dimensions 48 cm wide, 33 cm high, 10 cm deep. It is intact on the left and lower sides, but appears to be damaged on the top and the right; it is roughly finished on the reverse. The stone bears two lines of Greek text, with a deep horizontal line above each (cut to the same depth as the letters). The letters are neatly and regularly cut (given the coarse material). Although the stone is damaged top and right, there is no clear evidence that the text is cut short (the surface

⁷² Carini, 1874, p. 511, no. XII; cf. Agnello, 1953, no.11 (who offers no apparatus). It should be noted, however, that Orsi misreads the final letter of line 6 as an *epsilon*, rather than *sigma* (misled by damage to the stone).

⁷³ Marchese, 2012, p. 22, n. 111 with Appendix II.1 for 13 unpublished fragments (not, I think, registered in *SEG*).

⁷⁴ I have additionally so far identified *Taccuino* 1, p. 68, no.74 = *CIL* X.7162; *Tacc.* 1, p. 70, no. 81 = *CIL* X.7159; and thanks to Orsi's drawings, I have so far been able to identify at least six more of these monumental Latin fragments in the museum stores, which will be published fully in due course.

⁷⁵ See Tréziny, 2018, pp. 277-284.

is intact beyond the letters, and the horizontal lines also cease before the edge). The letters of line 1 are 7-7.5 cm tall; line 2, 6-7 cm; interlinear gap of 2-3 cm; the dividing lines are 11 cm apart; the *vacat* below line 2 is c.8 cm high. A Latin cross (7 cm) occupies the first position of line 1.

†ΞΕΝ
ΒΑΣΛΚ

The *xsi* is made of five equal strokes, horizontal and diagonal; the *epsilon* has bars of equal length; the *beta* has rounded closed eyes, of which the lower is substantially larger than the upper; the *alpha* has a left downward sloping cross-bar, and an extended apex; *sigma* is lunate; *kappa* has full-length arms.

A comparable piece was published by M. T. Manni Piraino in 1975, which she states was found in 1965 to the east of the Hellenistic walls⁷⁶. That block is slightly larger, but in a poorer state of preservation. It is apparent that it bears, at least in part, the same text: line 1 clearly reads [-]ΞΕΝ[-], with a separating line below; line 2 reads [-]ΒΑΣΛ[-] (Manni Piraino read: . ΑΚΛ[-]). Manni Piraino believed that she could see traces of a third, and possibly a fourth line below, but Professor Tréziny, who kindly drew my attention to this second piece, does not consider these to be visible⁷⁷. The existence of two near identical blocks of this form clearly disproves Manni Piraino's hypothesis of a funerary inscription. The form of the text, with Greek capitals forming what seem to be opaque abbreviations, separated by substantial horizontal lines, has more in common with a number of other boundary markers [p.148] from eastern Sicily, usually assumed to belong to late antiquity⁷⁸. Several other blocks with Christian symbols were found in the vicinity of the Faro Cantera⁷⁹. The precise interpretation of the letters, however, remains obscure.

It remains, perhaps, to be asked why Orsi's epigraphic acumen has been so frequently undervalued. This has not always been explicit (although cf. n.68 above), but his contributions are often passed over in silence, or even missed entirely. *Tacc.* 4, p. 44 [Fig. 10] contains neat drawings of four monumental [p.149] Latin fragments: «Litteris maximis et pulcherrimis (cm. 37.5) fragmenti quatuor exarata; in hortulo apud cubiculum custodis antiquitatum ad amphitheatrum». These were promptly published in *NSA*, 1889, p. 385, with the dimensions of all four blocks, and a note that they do not coincide with any of the fragments in *CIL X*. This is the fragmentary monumental text of a *Betilie[nus]*, several times republished since, and integral to debates over the Augustan or Severan date of the Syracusan amphitheatre. However, not one of the more recent publications seems to have noted that Orsi published the text (although Gentili quotes later correspondence from Orsi to G. E. Rizzo on the possible date of the inscription; and a second-century date, as there suggested by Orsi, remains the general consensus)⁸⁰. Doubtless part of the reason is that the vast majority of

⁷⁶ Manni Piraino, 1975, pp. 152-153, no.19 with tav. XXXIV.2 (ISic003698).

⁷⁷ I am most grateful to Prof. Tréziny for discussing this with me (correspondence in 2016), and for sharing a photograph of the upper part of the published piece; he additionally notes that the provenance as described by Manni Piraino cannot be confirmed, as it does not appear to correspond to any recorded excavation of 1965.

⁷⁸ See ISic001404 (Museo Archeologico Regionale di Adrano, inv. 480) and ISic001338, ISic004424, ISic004425, ISic004426 and 004427, all from the area inland of Catania.

⁷⁹ See Tréziny, 2018, pp. 283-284, figs. 423, 424.

⁸⁰ Not mentioned in Gentili, 1973, pp. 68-69 (and n.197 for the correspondence); or Wilson, 1980; or Buonocore, 1992, p. 119, no. 84 who states that the circumstances of discovery are unknown, attributing it to the early twentieth century. The blocks were last reported in the chiesetta di S. Nicolò, north of the amphitheatre.

Orsi's texts are presented as brief notices in the *Notizie*, constrained by the plain typographic format: these are, on the one hand, so numerous and scattered that they are easily missed and hard to unify; and on the other, this format encourages their treatment (and dismissal) as little more than notices of their existence. However, even his fullest epigraphic discussions are often ignored. Emblematic is his exemplary discussion of an archaic fragment from Akrai, in *NSA*, 1889, pp. 387-389 (inv. 6823 = ISic001478)⁸¹. Alongside a clear drawing and description, there is a sophisticated analysis of the letter forms, methodologically rigorous observations about isolated texts, the risks of drawing ethnic conclusions from letter forms, the typology of the text, and the epigraphic context of the material – it is an excellent example of extracting the maximum from a single, seemingly poor text (compare the unified treatment of the Megara Hyblaea material in *MAL* 1, 1890, cols. 786-789 after *Tacc.* 3, p. 19, noted above). Subsequent discussions make only the most cursory references to Orsi, while usually borrowing much of the content⁸². A final element in the puzzle is [p.150] doubtless that alluded to by Guarducci herself in her brief eulogy of 1935 – his willingness to consult others, such as Comparetti and Halbherr, which if read negatively can be taken to imply a lack of confidence or ability (and be used to belittle the contribution); it is of course anything but.

Ultimately, what the *Taccuini* reveal, when placed alongside his published output, and contextualised against his early career, is an epigraphist of the first order. This, however, is a 'militant epigrapher', subordinated to the larger vision of the militant archaeologist, as set out, for example, in the review of 1888 quoted above⁸³. The *Taccuini*, especially when made accessible in this excellent new edition, not only contribute new or additional information, but epigraphically they reveal the immense attention to detail – and the necessary understanding - which underpinned any epigraphic publication by Orsi. However, Orsi's priority (a lesson for any epigrapher, or archaeologist), was that of making the material available to the academic community, with the result that rarely did he devote extensive time or space to more detailed philological or historical elucidation – notwithstanding the fact that multiple examples illustrate his capacity to do so. The publication of the *Taccuini* is enormously to be welcomed. These first four alone, together with the earlier study by Marchese of the Vigna Cassia material, add over 100 unpublished texts to the 812 inscriptions that Orsi published, noted at the outset (and the final total will surely be over

⁸¹ The piece is described in detail in the inventory, and noted as recovered from the necropolis of the 'Pinnita' on 29 December 1888; however, on this occasion there seems to be no record of the piece in the *Taccuini*, notwithstanding the full account in *Taccuino* 2, pp. 104-114 of an expedition to Palazzolo, 27-31 December 1888, and explicit account of the Pinnita on pp. 110-114.

⁸² Noted by Guarducci 1949-1951, p. 104 (although not explicit that it is Orsi's drawing, etc. that she reproduces); but he serves as a straw man to make her argument about the Syracusan alphabet (a long-running debate with Jeffery); Pugliese Carratelli in republishing the piece altered the reading with little explanation (Pugliese Carratelli 1956, no. 19, not followed by later editors; moreover, his edition of no. 59 can be seen to be inferior to Orsi's unpublished drawing and description in *Tacc.* 2, p. 49; cf. no. 53 = *Tacc.* 1, p. 49 and no.54 = *Tacc.* 1, p. 48).

⁸³ Anecdotally, I once asked an eminent European epigrapher at what point they considered themselves to have become an 'epigraphist'; the response was a firm rebuttal of the title and the declaration that there is no such thing, rather they were 'an ancient historian' who used epigraphic evidence.

Prag, J.R.W. 2021. 'Paolo Orsi, «un Modestissimo Cultore Della Epigrafia»: Paolo Orsi's Contribution to Sicilian Epigraphy as Illustrated by the Newly Published *Taccuini*'. *Rendiconti dell'Accademia Nazionale dei Lincei. Classe di Scienze Morali, Storiche e Filologiche*, Series 9, volume 32: 121–54.

1,000), while also offering valuable supplements to almost 300 texts published by others⁸⁴. The task of incorporating this additional contribution to the epigraphic documentation of eastern Sicily will be substantial; but, together with the *Taccuini* themselves, would constitute a fitting recognition of Paolo Orsi, 'l'epigrafista'.

⁸⁴ Worthy of note for future study is Orsi's autopsy of the problematic numerals in four galleries of the Castello Eurialo fortress, in *Taccuino 2*, p. 41 (ISic000419); also *Taccuino 2*, p. 94 contains a report of a text from Cava d'Ispica which provides an alternative reading to existing traditions (ISic001073 = Paci 2005, no7 = IG XIV.253).

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Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9a

Fig. 9b.

Fig. 10

